

Original Research Article

Job appraisal effects on nurses and output of their work

Tabinda Kanwal^{1*}, Kousar Parveen², Muhammad Afzal³, Syed Amir Gilani⁴

Abstract

¹Post RN student, Lahore school of nursing, The university of Lahore

²Assistant Professor, Lahore school of nursing, The university of Lahore

³HOD, Lahore school of nursing, The university of Lahore

⁴Dean, FAHS, The university of Lahore

*Corresponding Author's Email:
tabindamalik5533@gmail.com

Job satisfaction of nurses with performance appraisal is very important for enhancing their motivation and work output. The health care setups have vast participation of the employees and appreciate them according to their work through performance appraisal. The purpose of this study was the effects of job satisfaction on nurses and their work output. The study was descriptive cross sectional. A total of 114 participants were taken for this study. The questionnaire was distributed to 114 participants and 100 participants returned back. The data was collected from "The Children's Hospital and Institute of Child Health, Lahore". The data is analyzed by using the SPSS version 16. Results of this study showed that nurses' ages were 21-25 years (31%), 26-30 years (52%), 31-35 years (11%) and above 36 years were 6%. Nursing is a female dominant profession, so all the participants were female nurses. The nurses experience 4-8 years (64%). Their chances of promotion were very less because of less structured policies. Only 44% satisfied from the present policies. Just 9% of participants got satisfied from the developed professional skills. 16% of participants agreed with the work distribution. There were increased workload and limited resources. The study showed that nursing is a female dominant profession. The employees were not appreciated unless the organization had limited resources. The participants were not satisfied with the policies. Increased workload decreases their quality of work. The following factors affect nurses' job satisfaction, if they work on them, job satisfaction will be improved with the limited resources. This study also covers the behavior effects regarding job satisfaction.

Keywords: Goals, Job appraisal, Productivity, Proficiencies, Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Performance appraisal is a job performance to review or evaluate the employees. It evaluates the employee's expertise, gaining and growing or deficiencies. Performance appraisal comprises different organizational processes e.g. measurements, formation of objectives and reward.

Through performance appraisal, estimates of the growth or deficiencies of employees are done, and it was also estimated that the employee deserves more training or growth further. The development of the staff productivity and effectiveness is a very major organizational strength in performance appraisal. One of the major roles of a manager is to gain the goals of the organization and to encourage the quality of service, that

is successful evaluation of workers (Akinbowale et al., 2013).

It can be well known that the understanding of employees from the process of performance appraisal, has a remarkable and positive link with performance and commitment of organization. Giving the attention, employees satisfaction is important for achieving effectual performances (Tripathi, 2001; Paul et al., 2014; Puranik and Choudhar, 2014).

Performance appraisal is an important part that guides and manages career progress in the health care setting. It is considered a major tool for work effectiveness and health care setups to succeed further more. In the hospital setting, through performance appraisal motivated

the staff nurses by appreciating their work. They work more effectively and give their best. Performance appraisal is a major component of human resources management. Their results are used for making decisions at managerial side and for a number of other purposes, e.g. research purpose. Through the appraisal process, the organizations select and hire the new employees and expand the previous staff as well as encouraging them by giving reward on their good performances. Performance appraisal is a process of assessing and evaluating the employee performances. Basically it is a method in which the manager or supervisor appreciates the employees on their work bases (Malik and Aslam, 2013; Puranik and Choudhar, 2014; Joseph, 2014; Singh and Rana, 2015).

Performance appraisal is a continuous process of estimating employees work performances and their outcomes (Malik and Aslam, 2013; Puranik and Choudhar, 2014)

Through performance appraisal, managers know the employee weakness, strengths and make new plans for improving weaknesses, and also motivate by appreciating their positive points (Jamil and Raja, 2011; Ahmad and Shahzad, 2011; Joseph, 2014; Singh and Rana, 2015).

Performance appraisal is effectively a performance managing tool. It gives data reports and also factors of the management process. Performance appraisal gives better motivation, performance of work and efficiency if it is used objectively. On the other hand, if it is used unsuitably, their effects will be devastating (Caruth et al., 2014; Khan, 2013).

Consequently, employee satisfaction and motivation is necessary through performance appraisal for getting quality of work and productivity. Employees dissatisfaction from the performance appraisal process is considered as an organizational disease symptom. So, the management should know the hurdles which warp the satisfaction of employees by using the process of performance appraisal. They should take appropriate and effective steps and increase their attempts for finishing these hurdles (Grub, 2007)

A lot of studies were conducted to examine the relationship between the satisfaction of employees with the process of performance appraisal, to motivate their performances of work and productivity in many setups. There is a deficiency of studies that pivot on satisfaction with the process of performance appraisal, in those employees working in hospital or health care setups (Mullins, 2002; Ojokuku, 2013).

So by conducting this study, we tried to assess the influences of satisfaction in nurses regarding the process of performance appraisal on nurses inner motivation and outcomes of their work in the shape work performances, efficiency and also recognize the effects of motivating the nurses work (Malik and Aslam 2014).

Moreover, this study attempts to recognize the hurdles which retarded the satisfaction of nurses with the process

of performance appraisal. The participation of nurses in revising and bettering the process of performance appraisal helps to achieve satisfaction (Ali et a, 2012).

Nurses, who worked longer had much experience of work and skills, they were doing good work than newly hired. Experienced nurses are more skillful and know how to provide quality of care in narrow situations (Ali et al., 2012; Adaeze, 2012).

Nurses job satisfaction through appraisal is very important for enhancing their inner motivation and gaining excellent output. The previously conducted studies showed that nurses were less appreciated than their job responsibilities. They were not satisfied with the job appraisal. The organizational management needs to appreciate nurses and their work. In that way, a successful organization can achieve their work goals (Purnik and Choudhar, 2014).

The nurses' dissatisfaction can create disharmony and their effects will be disastrous. Organizational appreciation for nurses will create a sense of harmony, satisfaction and motivation in them. They will provide more quality of work. The organization achieves the task given to the nurses successfully. Their motivations had positive effects on inner satisfaction and also their work. They can face any challenge for the completion of their task. Nurses work output and level of performance will increase. They work efficiently and have more delegates (Malik and Aslam, 2013).

Literature review

Performance appraisal always does not expand productivity since it may be influenced sometimes by ion content errors, conflict linking, the needs of employees and goals of appraisal (Giangreco et al., 2012).

Nurse appraisal purposes are given as follows; to find out professional proficiencies, to increase staff growth and encourage them regarding higher achievements (Tomey, 2004).

For attaining an efficient system of performance appraisal, authentication of appraisal only tools is not adequate but also the response of employees to this system is much important. Dissatisfaction and unfairness in the process of performance appraisal will lead to failure (Basavanthapa, 2003; Akramullah et al., 2011). Many of the methods of evaluation of performance appraisal are not effective due to complex Spence and wood (2007).

Zaboli, Delgoshate and Haghani (2005), said that crucial factors of effectiveness of performance appraisal of nurses are unfamiliarity from performance appraisal goals and conflict.

Hamidi et al. (2009) reported that performance appraisal results had an effect on enhancing the motivation of employees, the absence of fairness, goals, adequate responses and the participation of staff.

Hysong et al. (2006) noted that in hospital settings, lack of trained managers is the major issue (weak point) of the appraisal system of employees. It plays a vital role in a system of organization success. When nurses are appreciated through their performance appraisal, it enhances their motivation and they give better outcomes. According to the report, it is noted that the performance appraisal system of nurses is not effective and nurses are not completely satisfied.

It is revealed that performance appraisal systems that are implemented are deficient and also poor in knowledge. Duffin (2006) revealed that the performance appraisal system in health care setting is imperfect, six out of ten NHS staff receives appraisal. Although, the guidelines of government recommended that the nurses have authority in delivery of care to support the management. This shows that the performance appraisal of nurses creates satisfaction and motivates them for better outcomes.

DH (1993), said that every person's capacities and needs differ from each other. There is need to value every person's work. Maslows (1943) need of hierarchy is that people cannot be moved and evolve when they are not supported or given importance. Walker and Jones (2004) stated that it is important to be familiar with everyone's skills and notion. It requires self confidence looking for justification and feedback offering. Organizations need to adopt those practices to motivate, attract and keep their employees (Lepak and Gowan, 2010). By using the practices of human resources management, they can overcome employees' attitude towards work for doing their work efficiently and honestly (Collins and Clark, 2003). Performance appraisal is the source to measure the employees work efficiencies (Redman et al., 2000).

Through a performance appraisal process, an organization can evaluate the employee work, performing their work standard (Ikramullah et al., 2012), and can also motivate those employees who are not working efficiently (Scott and Einstein, 2001).

It is the duty of the organization to take pure, accurate measures of performance appraisal assessment results. Mostly, fairness is ignored while making results on the basis of performance appraisal. Many of the employees work deliberately but do not get appreciation (Korsgaard and Roberson, 1995), performance appraisal influence on their work output, behavior, etc. Performance appraisal gives motivation to employees for improving their work more.

It is concluded that there are assessable issues on appraisal equality and accuracy (Boxall and Purcell, 2003; Swierez et al., 2010). On the bases of performance appraisal, minor equality is noted which is not enough (Swierczetal, 2012). In the nursing profession, justifiable equality is ignored. The performance appraisal results on the bases of fairness showed more skills and behavior towards work (Boxall and Purcell, 2003). Singh Sanjeet

(2011) stated that the influence of performance appraisal on organization and individuals, considerable effects were seen on both.

MianKhasro (2012) conducted a study and said that employees' output totally depends on organization appraisal. If they appraise their work honestly, employees will work more efficiently. On the other side, poor appraisal dissatisfy the workers and they will not enjoy the work.

Khushbu (2014) revealed that there is a need to appreciate the nurses work in hospitals. Their quality of work increases and gives more output than expected time limits. Performance appraisal makes the organization system work more effectively and powerfully and employees participation will increase thereby devoting extra working hours for achieving organizational goals. The employees turnover increases and it leads the organization towards progress and prosperity (Brown and Peterson, 1993). Mayer and Allen (1993), said that effective devotion relates to employees loyalty, fairness and organization participation.

Objectives

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effects on nurses performance appraisal. To assess the job satisfaction of nurses from performance appraisal.

Problem statement

The problem was lack of time of nurses participants due to their workload. So, data is usually collected after duty hours.

Operational definition

The operational definition was the effects of job appraisal on nurses which helps to achieve their goals and work productivity.

Significance

The study will help to improve skills and they give excellent outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

Study design: It was cross- sectional descriptive study.

Study setting: The study was conducted from, The children hospital and the institute of child health Lahore.

Table 1. Demographic data

Variables	Total no.%
Age:	
21-25 years	31%
26-30 years	52%
31-35 years	11%
Above 36 years	6%
Sex:	
Females	All were females
Work experience:	
1-3 years	26%
4-8 years	64%
9- 13 years	7%
14-18 years	3%

Duration of study: The study duration was (1 month), 3 March to 3 April, 2021.

Sample technique: A simple random technique was used to collect data.

Sample Selection

Inclusion criteria

The data was collected by those nurses who were 21-40 years of age and work experience 1-18years.

Exclusion criteria

Outdoor department nurses excluded. Those nurses excluded who didn't agree for participation in this study.

Equipments

A questionnaire was used to collect data from participants. The questionnaire was taken from (Alpern et al., 2013). It has two parts; Demographic data taken in first part. In the second part, the participants percentage to assess job satisfaction.

Data analyzing: The data was analyzed by SPSS version 16.

Ethical consideration

Consent was taken in written form from participants. All the collected data and information were kept confidentially. It is informed that they can withdraw the study at any time.

RESULTS

In table 1, results showed that the participants' age was 21 to 36 years above (maximum 40). Maximum members who participated in this study were 52% and their ages were 26-30 years. Meanwhile, only 6% of participants were included above 36 years old. The study participants all were females. 64% were the maximum participants who had their work experience 4-8 years and the minimum 3% participants who had work experience 14-18 years were included in this study.

DISCUSSION

The study was conducted to assess the performance appraisal on nurses job satisfaction. The research is conducted at The Children's Hospital and Institute of Child Health Lahore.

The target population was Pakistan female nurses. On the other hand, the accessible population was The Children's Hospital and The Institute of Child Health, Lahore. Sample size was 100. The results showed that all the population were female nurses because nursing is a female dominant profession. 52% of participants' age range was between 26-30 years and having maximum job experience which shows that they have an active role in delivering efficient and cost effective care.

The managers check the performances on a daily basis, give their suggestions to improve nursing skills and appraisal for good work that will increase the spirit to do quality work. The knowledge and skills can improve nursing care services and decrease the ratio of morbidity and mortality rate. There was good collaborative interpersonal communication between the team members (54%).

On the other hand, there were some factors that contributed or affected job satisfaction: The employees were not encouraged by supervisors. Only 18% of employees were encouraged by supervisors. There are

Table 2. Participants percentages

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1.The management of this system is supportive.	11%	7%	45%	37%
2. I receive the right amount of support and guidance from my supervisor.	21%	13%	37%	29%
3. I have learned many new skills in this position.	3%	5%	54%	38%
4. I feel encouraged by my supervisor to offer suggestions and improvements.	25%	35%	18%	22%
5. I am appropriately recognized when I perform well at my regular work duties.	4%	10%	33%	53%
6. I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.	44%	26%	19%	11%
7.I have adequate opportunities to develop my professional skills.	43%	31%	9%	17%
8.The amount of work I am expected to finish is reasonable.	42%	33%	16%	9%
9.My work is evaluated on the bases of fair system of performance standards.	12%	11%	42%	35%
10. My department provides all the equipment and resources necessary for performing a duty.	39%	30 %	25%	6%
11. My colleagues and I work well together.	14%	21%	34%	31%
12. I feel I can easily communicate with my members .	9%	6%	54%	31%

less opportunities or promotion due to less structured policies. The policies were not updated properly. 44% participants were satisfied with the present policies. There was no adequacy of developing professional skills due to study barriers. 9% of participants were satisfied with adequacy of developed professional skills. Chronically unstuffed, increased workload decreased the quality of work. 16% of participants agreed with work distribution. 39% of participants strongly disagree with the adequacy of equipment and resources.

Limitations

The study was directed in a short time period. The data was taken from one setup and it showed the result of job appraisal effects on nurses and their work output.

CONCLUSION

There were various factors that affect nurses' job satisfaction and if they are worked on, job satisfaction will be improved with the limited resources. We are working in an under-developing country where there are limited resources but the manpower if appropriately used, we can win the battle. There is a need to encourage their work for achieving better outcomes. This study covered only the behavioral effects regarding job satisfaction but it included different aspects of study. Therefore, in future the other researchers can conduct study on it. There is further need to improve management skills at the clinical side to improve job satisfaction and to promote well

defined structured policies for the promotion of their satisfaction. There is also a need to improve our health care resources to meet the criteria of need. It will be time consuming but nothing is impossible .The government should take action on it.

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